

Finite Element implementation of the Coupled Criterion based on the Principle of Minimum Total Energy subjected to a Stress Condition to predict crack onset and growth

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Finite Fracture Mechanics

Stress and Energy Criterion

PMTE-SC

Abstract A numerical procedure predicting crack onset and growth in brittle materials is developed using the Coupled Criterion of Finite Fracture Mechanics (CCFFM) [1] which assumes crack advances by finite steps and requires both stress and energy conditions are fulfilled. Crack advances are bridged by a continuous distribution of springs, similarly to the Linear Elastic-(perfectly) Brittle Interface Model (LEBIM) [2] combined with CCFFM [3]. The Principle of Minimum Total Energy subjected to a Stress Condition (PMTE-SC) [4,5] is implemented by a load stepping algorithm, minimizing the total energy change due to a crack advance allowed by the stress criterion. The PMTE-SC appears to be more versatile than the classical formulation of CCFFM using stress and energy criterion curves, providing a tool to solve complex problems of industrial relevance.

A simple implementation of PMTE-SC in FEM code Abaqus considers cracks geometrically modelled as topological discontinuities in the finite element mesh, with cracks introduced explicitly during the discretization of the domain, the crack faces coinciding with the element edges. Several numerical examples are solved, showing that accurate predictions are obtained for short cracks, holes and notches.

References:

[1] D. Leguillon, 2002. Strength or toughness? A criterion for crack onset at a notch. *European Journal of Mechanics A/Solids*, 21, 61–72.

[2] V. Mantič, L. Távara, A. Blázquez, E. Graciani, F. París, 2015. A linear elastic-brittle interface model: application for the onset and propagation of a fibre-matrix interface crack under biaxial transverse loads. *International Journal of Fracture* 195, 15-38.

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[4] V. Mantič, 2014. Prediction of initiation and growth of cracks in composites. Coupled stress and energy criterion of the finite fracture mechanics (Keynote Lecture). In: *Proceedings of the 16th European Conference on Composite Materials (ECCM16)*, F. París (Ed.), <http://www.escm.eu.org/eccm16/assets/1252.pdf>.

[5] M. Muñoz-Reja, V. Mantič, L. Távara, 2022. Comparative analytical study of the coupled criterion and the principle of minimum total energy with stress condition applied to linear elastic interfaces. *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics*, 103274.

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